

Studies on Physico-Chemical Properties of Solid Catalyst: Thermal Analysis, Infrared Spectroscopy, X-Ray Diffraction and Surface Area Measurements of Nickel Molybdate, Nickel Tungstate and Cobalt Tungstate

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Thermal characteristics of nickel molybdate ($\text{NiMoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), nickel tungstate ($\text{NiWO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and cobalt tungstate ($\text{CoWO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) have been studied by DTA and TG techniques and different transition products have been characterised by IR and X-ray analysis. The DTA thermogram of nickel molybdate exhibits two endothermic peaks at 185° and 390° and an exothermic peak at 420°. The TG curve records a continuous weight loss of 7.9% within the temperature range 30°-385°. The DTA thermogram of nickel tungstate exhibits one endothermic peak at 214° followed by a sharp exothermic peak at 458°. The TG thermogram records a gradual weight loss, within the temperature range 30°-390° amounting to 11.87%. The DTA curve of cobalt tungstate shows one endothermic peak at 218° and an exothermic peak at 418°. The TG thermogram of cobalt tungstate registers a continuous weight loss within the temperature ranges 30°-360° amounting to 10.14%. The surface areas of the catalysts were measured at different temperatures by BET method. The results of DTA and TG have been correlated with X-ray, IR spectroscopy and surface area measurements.

NICKEL molybdate, nickel tungstate and cobalt tungstate are reported to be good catalysts for oxidation, hydrogenation, dehydrogenation, aromatisation and desulfurisation reactions¹⁻¹¹. Literature on the structural properties of the molybdates and tungstates is extremely meagre. In the present paper the results of investigation on the physicochemical properties of nickel molybdate, nickel tungstate and cobalt tungstate by DTA, TG, IR, X-ray diffraction and surface area measurements have been reported.

Experimental

Preparation of the catalysts:

A. *Nickel molybdate*: A boiling solution of nickel nitrate hexahydrate (45 g./250 ml) was slowly added with stirring to a boiling solution of sodium molybdate dihydrate (62.5 g./250 ml). The precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried at 100°, ground to 100 mesh size and chemically analysed¹².

B. *Nickel tungstate*: A hot solution of sodium tungstate dihydrate (45 g./150 ml of boiled water) was slowly added to a solution of nickel nitrate hexahydrate (35 g./100 ml of boiled water) with constant stirring. The pale green precipitate was filtered, washed with boiled water and then with cold water, dried at 110°, ground to 100 mesh size and chemically analysed¹³.

C. *Cobalt tungstate*: A hot solution of cobaltous nitrate (29 g./100 ml) was slowly added with stirring

to a solution of sodium tungstate (35 g./150 ml). The violet precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried at 110°, ground to about 100 mesh size and chemically analysed.

Experimental procedure:

The experimental set up and the procedure followed by the authors for various measurements, DTA, TG, IR and X-ray diffraction were the same as reported by Bhattacharyya *et al.*^{14,15}.

Result and Discussion

Nickel molybdate:

(i) *Thermal analysis*: The DTA and TG curves in air are shown in Fig. 1. DTA curve shows one endothermic peak at 185° (range 30°-340°) followed by a small endothermic dent at 390° and an exothermic peak at 420° (range 395°-443°). Similar type of DTA curve was obtained in nitrogen atmosphere indicating that the exothermic peak may not be due to oxidation. The TG curve registers a continuous weight loss of about 7.9% within the temperature range, 30°-385°, which corresponds to the removal of one molecule of water from one molecule of $\text{NiMoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. After 385° the weight loss is negligible, ensuring that after this temperature the substance undergoes changes which are not accompanied by weight loss. The endothermic dent at 390° and the exothermic peak at 420° give indications that the

molybdate starts decomposing followed by crystallisations of the component, oxides, MoO_3 and NiO .

are more or less absent; the bands, which have been observed are due to Mo-O stretching.

Fig. 1. DTA and TG curve of nickel molybdate in air.

(ii) *Infrared studies*: The ir spectrum of the nickel molybdate catalyst heated at 110° , 340° and 510° are shown in Fig. 2(a) and 2(b). The figure indicates

(iii) *X-ray diffraction studies*: The original sample exhibits the X-ray diffraction pattern which identifies its structure to be $\text{NiMoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (d values = 4.07, 3.31 and 3.02 Å). In the X-ray diffraction pattern of the catalyst heated at 340° some more well defined and strong lines ($d = 6.30, 4.62, 4.03, 3.50, 3.28, 3.08$ and 2.73) appear indicating more crystalline structure of the nickel molybdate catalyst and the onset of the decomposition of the molybdate. The X-ray diffraction pattern of the catalyst heated at 510° exhibits some more lines whose d -values are identical with those reported for MoO_3 ($d = 6.60, 3.50, 3.32, 3.27, 3.10, 1.72$ and 1.63 Å) and NiO ($d = 2.75, 2.73, 2.18, 1.99$ and 1.50 Å) in A.S.T.M. files. Therefore, the nickel molybdate catalyst heated at 510° is the mixture of NiO and MoO_3 . The X-ray diffraction pattern of the catalyst heated at 960° is the same as that of the catalyst heated at 510° . The thermal curves (Fig. 1) indicates the changes at 390° and 420° which may be attributed to the onset of decomposition and immediate crystallisation of decomposed product of nickel molybdate. The concentration of the decomposed product increases with increasing temperature and therefore at 510° and above the d -value gives clear evidence of the decomposition of nickel molybdate to NiO and

Fig. 2a. Infrared spectra of nickel molybdate (a) at 110° and (b) at 340° .

Fig. 2b. Infrared spectra of nickel molybdate (c) at 510° .

clearly that the sample heated at 110° gives bands due to both Mo-O stretching vibration, as observed in the case of normal molybdates, and O-H stretching and H-O-H bending motion of lattice water^{16,17}. At higher temperature, 340° and above the characteristic bands of O-H stretching and H-O-H bending

MoO_3 . As the decomposition of the nickel molybdate is a slow process being a solid phase reaction, the presence of undecomposed nickel molybdate would be observed by X-ray diffraction studies unless the sample is heated for a very long time at high temperatures.

As it is difficult to compute the percentage of decomposition unless detailed X-ray diffraction studies are made, attempt has not been made for computation of the percentage decomposition.

(iv) *Surface area measurement*: The surface areas of the nickel molybdate catalyst were measured at 110°, 340°, 390° and 420° and found to be 54.9, 56.75, 52.5 and 39.17 m²/g. The values of surface area remain almost constant within the range 110°–380° after which it decreases. It may be concluded that the catalytic activity of the nickel molybdate should be maximum after complete dehydration.

The course of thermal changes occurring in nickel molybdate may be represented as follows:

Nickel tungstate:

(i) *Thermal analysis*: The DTA and TG curves in air are shown in Fig. 3. The DTA curve shows one endothermic peak at 214° (range 30°–390°) followed by a sharp endothermic peak at 458°. Similar type

Fig. 3. DTA and TG curves of nickel tungstate in air.

of DTA curve was found in nitrogen atmosphere indicating that the exothermic peak may not be due to oxidation. The TG curve registers a gradual weight loss within the temperature range 30°–390°, amounting to about 11.87% which corresponds to the removal of two molecules of water from one molecule of NiWO₄·2H₂O. After 390° the weight loss is negligible ensuring that after this temperature the substance undergoes a change which is not followed by weight loss.

(ii) *Infrared studies*: The ir spectrum of the nickel tungstate catalyst heated at different transition temperatures is shown in Fig. 4. The ir spectrum of the catalyst heated at 110° shows a number of bands, which may be attributed to O–H stretching, wagging and rocking and H–O–H bending motion of lattice water etc.^{16,17} and also to W–O stretching vibration. The catalyst heated at 430°, 525° and 935° gives bands at 870 and 810 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to W–O stretching, as observed in the case of normal tungstate. This observation indicates that the compound does not undergo any type of decomposition upto 935°.

(iii) *X-ray diffraction studies*: The X-ray diffraction pattern of the sample heated at 110° is indicative of amorphous structure of the catalyst. The X-ray analysis of the catalyst heated at 430° exhibited weak and strong lines (*d* = 2.89 and 2.46 Å) which indicate poorly crystalline structure of the catalyst. In the X-ray diffraction pattern of the catalyst heated at 525° a number of weak and strong lines (*d* = 4.60, 3.70, 3.55, 2.88, 2.45 and 1.67 Å) appeared indicating that the structure of the catalyst is more ordered and crystalline. However, the X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples heated at 525° and 935° are the same indicating that at or above 525° there is no change in the crystal structure of the catalyst. Therefore from X-ray analysis it may be concluded that exothermic peak at 458° may be due to disorder-order phase transition.

The thermal changes of nickel tungstate may, therefore, be represented as follows:

Fig. 4. Infrared spectra of nickel tungstate (a) at 110°, (b) 430°, and (c) 525°.

(iv) *Surface area measurement* : The surface areas of the nickel tungstate catalyst were measured at 110°, 430° and 525° and were found to be 14.67 m²/g, 23.24 m²/g and 6.77 m²/g respectively. The maximum surface area corresponds to the temperature of complete dehydration (at about 430°) and the minimum to the complete crystallisation. Therefore, it may be anticipated that the nickel tungstate catalyst should show maximum catalytic activity at this temperature region, which is confirmed by the works of Beuther and Flinn⁹ and Holder and Welty⁵.

Cobalt tungstate :

(i) *Thermal analysis* : The DTA and TG curve of cobalt tungstate in air are shown in Fig. 5. In

Fig. 5. DTA and TG curves of cobalt tungstate in air.

the DTA curve one flat endothermic peak appears at 215° (range 30°–360°) followed by an exothermic peak at 418° (range 410°–445°). The TG curve registers a continuous weight loss within the temperature range, 30°–360°. The total weight loss amounts to about 10.14%, which corresponds to the removal of two molecules of water from one molecule of $\text{CoWO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Therefore, the endothermic peak at 215° may be due to dehydration. After 360°,

the weight loss in TG curve is negligible indicating thereby that the exothermic peak may be due to some kind of phase change not involving any weight loss.

(ii) *Infrared studies* : The ir spectrum of the cobalt tungstate catalyst heated at different transition temperatures are shown in Fig. 6. The spectrum of the original sample of cobalt tungstate shows a large number of bands which may be attributed to O–H stretching, wagging and rocking and H–O–H bending^{16,17} and W–O stretching. The spectra of the samples heated at 360° and 475° give bands characteristics of W–O stretching as observed in the case of normal tungstate. The results indicate that cobalt tungstate does not undergo decomposition after dehydration even upto 500°.

(iii) *X-ray diffraction studies* : The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples of cobalt tungstate heated at 110° and 360° exhibited very weak lines indicating the amorphous structure of the catalyst at these temperatures. However, in the diffraction pattern of the catalyst heated at 475° more lines of strong and bright intensities ($d = 2.95, 2.45, 2.07, 1.90, 1.50, 1.03, 1.00, 0.78$) appeared indicating that the structure of the catalyst was more ordered and crystalline at this temperature. Therefore, the exothermic peak at 418° may be due to crystallisation.

Thus, the thermal changes in cobalt tungstate may be expressed as follows :

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Fig. 6. Infrared spectra of cobalt tungstate (a) at 110°, (b) 360° and (c) 475°.

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